

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D7.1 Project Management Handbook

WP7- Project Management

Version: 1.0

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© CALIPER Consortium, 2020

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document information

Grant Agreement Number	873134		Acronym	CALIPER	
Full Title	The CALIPER project: Linking research and innovation for gender equality				
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans				
Funding scheme	CSA – Coordination and Support Action				
Start Date	1 st January 2020	Duration	48 months		
Project URL	http://caliper-project.eu/				
EU Project Officer	Katherine QUEZADA, REA, Unit B5				
Project Coordinator	Vasiliki Moumtzi - ViLabs				
Deliverable	D7.1. Project Management Handbook				
Work Package	WP7 – Project Management				
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M3	Actual	M3 (30 March 2020)	
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P - Public		
Lead Beneficiary	VIL				
Keywords	Project management				

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.10	13/03/2020	Draft	1st control level: First draft shared among partners	VIL
0.20	20/03/2020	Draft	Report updated based on contribution	ALL PARTNERS
1.00	31/03/2020	Final	2nd level check – Ready for submission	VIL

Executive Summary

This report illustrates the CALIPER project management handbook. It will be used by the consortium as a reference to organise all research activities addressing the contractual obligations towards the European Commission.

In particular, the handbook includes the procedures, rules, and standards. These guidelines will be adopted by all consortium members to follow a common operational methodology aiming at reducing the project overhead and in the meantime, increasing the productivity and quality of the work carried out. Therefore, it is an obligation that all partners are aware of the important general aspects addressed in this report to successfully implement the project activities.

Contents

1	Introduction.....	7
1.1	Purpose & Scope.....	7
1.2	Indented audience.....	7
1.3	Structure of the deliverable	7
1.4	Relation to other WPs & Tasks	7
2	Project management.....	8
2.1	The structure	8
2.2	Roles	9
2.3	Communication and collaboration procedures.....	14
2.3.1	Internal communication.....	14
2.3.2	External communication	18
2.4	Monitoring and reporting procedure	19

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Management Organisation Structure.....	8
Figure 2: Screenshot of Task Boards within the Project Management Tool	16
Figure 3: Screenshot of Milestones within the Project Management Tool.....	16
Figure 4: Screenshot of the File Repository within the Project Management Tool	17
Figure 5: Screenshot of Links within the Project Management Tool	17
Figure 6: Screenshot of the Chat within the Project Management Tool.....	18

Table of Tables

Table 1: The CALIPER Steering Committee	10
Table 2: The CALIPER Project Management Team	12
Table 3: CALIPER Advisory Board.....	13
Table 4: Physical meetings schedule	14
Table 5: Periodic reporting time-plan	20

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The aim of this document is to describe the project management structures and procedures in the CALIPER project. This deliverable defines a consistent plan and a set of communication and collaboration procedures to guarantee that the effective progress of the project implementation. The management procedures presented in this document are applicable to all the activities of the project. Hence, compliance to these procedures is mandatory for all partners.

1.2 Indented audience

This document should be used as a reference by:

- The CALIPER Project Coordinator and the Quality and Risk Manager
- all Consortium Partners of CALIPER
- Any other person who will join the partner's working teams at a later stage.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The Chapter 2 begins with a presentation of the project management approach. It is the foundation of the project management procedures defined in this document. It contains the definition of consortium member roles, the procedures that partners should follow during the internal/external communication and collaboration activities, and the procedures for the project progress monitoring.

1.4 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The project management handbook applies horizontally and equally at all the project WPs.

2 Project management

Project management core purpose is to control the progress of each work package, to coordinate the different project activities and to implement the quality control mechanisms (see D7.2). The project management covers administrative, financial, and research aspects. The CALIPER project is divided into eight Work Packages and these are in turn divided into Tasks, relevant to the goals and structure of each WP. Every Task has the number of partners required to fulfil the goals of the specific activity, and one of them is the leader. Overall, one partner, based on its role and expertise may contribute to more than one activity within one or more WPs.

2.1 The structure

The CALIPER work plan requires an efficient and effective operation of the consortium to ensure that all activities are achieved within time, and within budget, and any other resource constraints. Therefore, a well-defined management structure has been put into place, according to the guidelines of the [PMI](#) (Project Management Institute) and the [PMIBOK](#) (PMI Body of Knowledge). The project management in CALIPER will guarantee transparency and commitment to all engaged partners and thus facilitate an unobstructed and successful project evolution. The objective is to ensure that the project will meet its objectives on time, on budget, and with high quality results.

Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project such as CALIPER, is Small project, thus the Governance Structure is simple and aligns in the following formation (Figure 1). Overall, the **Coordinator** interacts with the EU and the parties about the project. The **Steering Committee** is the main decision-making body of the project. It consists of the project Coordinator, and one member from each partner organisation. The **Project Management Team** is the high-level management body and it consists of the project Coordinator, the Scientific/ GEP Manager, the RRI Manager, the Risk and Quality Manager and the WP Leaders. The roles of the Governance structure are described in the next Chapter.

Figure 1: Management Organisation Structure

2.2 Roles

The organisational structure of the CALIPER consortium is comprised of the following Consortium Bodies:

At decision-making level:

The **Steering Committee** as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. It is the main decision-making body of the project. It consists of the Project Coordinator, and one member from each partner organisation. Its role is described at the CALIPER Consortium Agreement:

*The **Steering Committee (SC)** will be the main decision-making body of the project. It will consist of the Project Coordinator (PC), and one member from each partner organisation. The role of the SC will be to manage the project in a smooth and successful way dealing with financial, legal and administrative issues. It will monitor and assess the actual progress and direction of the project and the accomplishment of project objectives. It is also responsible for the resources used and the costs incurred. Recommendations for amendments to the work plan, major technical, financial and resource allocation decisions along with periodic and final reports will be submitted to the SC for ratification, including without limitation, decisions regarding: (a) wider communication direction of the project; (b) amendments to the description of work and effort allocation; (c) specific contractual issues with the EC and (d) financial planning and control and other administrative arrangements. To ensure successful project implementation and to evaluate external threats and opportunities, the SC will analyse the project performance indicators and all other relevant information provided by the Project Management Team. Meetings of the SC will be held during the project meetings, unless issues arise which require extraordinary meetings. The SC will take decisions upon a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast. In case there is no quorum (50% of the members +1), the SC will be reconvening in 4 weeks' time.*

Chapter 6.1 of the CALIPER Consortium Agreement, dated 20/11/2019

The table below presents the Steering Committee.

The CALIPER Steering Committee	
Beneficiary	Name
VIL (Project Coordinator)	Vasiliki Moumtzi
SV	Maria Sangiuliano
YAE	Mangala Srinivas
UZG	Anamari Nakic
SRNSF	Nino Gachechiladze
STU	Dagmar Cagáňová
ULB	Laurent Licata
NTUA	Emmanouil Ntanos
IRB	Maria Isabel Labrid
UEFISCDI	Elena Simion

YU	Gökay ÖZERİM
UNILE	Rosaria Rinaldi

Table 1: The CALIPER Steering Committee

At project implementation level:

The **Project Management Team** as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project which reports to and be accountable to the Steering Committee. It is the high-level management body of the CALIPER project. It consists of the Project Coordinator, the Scientific/ GEP Manager, the RRI Manager, the Risk and Quality Manager and the WP leaders (SV, ULB, UZG, STU BA).

The Project Management Team role, along with the responsibilities of the Scientific/ GEP Manager, the RRI Manager, the Risk and Quality Manager are described the CALIPER Consortium Agreement:

*The **Project Management Team (PMT)** will be the high-level management body of the CALIPER project. It will consist of the PC (VIL), Scientific/ GEP Manager (SGM), RRI Managers (RRIM), Risk and Quality Manager (RQM) and the WP leaders (SV, ULB, UZG, STU BA). Its main responsibility will be the scientific and operational management of the project. Scientific/GEP Manager (SGM) who will work closely with the PC, will be responsible for the overall project scientific implementation. The **SGM** will ensure the scientific cohesion and excellence of the project; it will collaborate with the GEP Working Groups, oversee their activities and progress, supervises the quality of scientific deliverables produced by the WPs. The **Responsible Research and innovation Manager (RRIM)** will guarantee that the project is proceeding in a responsible and ethically acceptable manner according to the recommended Responsible Research and Innovation aspects. **Risk and Quality Manager (RQM)** will lead be the early identification, assessment, and - along with the support of the PC- the management of administrative and technical risks, as well as the development of the Quality Plan, the implementation of the quality procedures and the verification of the project results. PMT's mission will be to assess overall WP progress and to propose corrections to the SC, if needed, according to the project strategy. The PMT has a different mission from the SC, which is the planning, executing and controlling of the different WPs both in technical and administrative level. It shall take charge of project progress and will decide upon all relevant WP technical and administrative issues. The PMT will also ensure the protection of IPRs and of the respective outputs, it will identify risks, draft contingency plans and survey ethical issues, including issues of responsible research and innovation, as well as data management. The PMT will convene monthly online meetings and will organise ad hoc meetings if necessary. The PMT will make decisions upon a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast. In case there is no quorum (50% of the members +1), the PMT will be reconvening in 4 weeks' time.*

Chapter 6.1 of the CALIPER Consortium Agreement, dated 20/11/2019

In addition, the responsibilities of the **project Coordinator** and **WP leaders** are described at the Consortium Agreement, as well.

*The **Project Coordinator (PC)** who will chair the Steering Committee, will be responsible for the overall management, communication, and coordination of the project following the GA requirements. In particular, the PC will monitor compliance of the partners with their*

obligations; keep the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available; collect, review to verify consistency and submit reports and other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the EC; transmit documents and information connected with the CALIPER project to the other Parties concerned; admin the financial contribution of the EC and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Payments Section of the Consortium agreement. Payments to partners are the exclusive tasks of the Coordinator; provide, upon request, the partners with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the PC when necessary for the Parties to present claims; chair all meetings of the SC, unless decided otherwise.

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for the successful execution of work at the level of the Work Package. They are also responsible for planning and implementing the contents in order to ensure that the milestones are met and that the deliverables are up-to-standard and submitted on time, monitoring their performance and guaranteeing the accomplishment of the project objectives. They will provide regular reports, control the quality and the schedule of the work, and actively participate in meetings. Every WP will be formed by experts/executives from each partner, with complementary expertise, according to the task allocation. They will guide the task leaders and contributors towards an efficient and effective collaboration, and they will share the deliverables with the other partners in order to get their feedback. They will also communicate regularly with the Project Coordinator in order to discuss potential delays and ways to tackle any problems that might arise. Task leaders and contributors will execute the respective tasks and will communicate with their WPLs on a regular basis. If any potential delays are identified in achieving/submitting the milestones and deliverables for which they are responsible, task leaders should report such delays to the WPLs and seek advice on how best to achieve the targets.

Chapter 6.2 of the CALIPER Consortium Agreement, dated 20/11/2019

The table below includes the Project Management Team.

The CALIPER Project Management Team		
Role	Beneficiary	Name
Project Coordinator	VIL	Vasiliki Moumtzi
Scientific/ GEP Manager	SV	Maria Sangiuliano
RRI Manager	VIL	Vasiliki Madesi
Risk and Quality Manager	VIL	Vasiliki Moumtzi
WP1 Leader	SV	Maria Sangiuliano
WP2 Leader	ULB	Sara Aguirre
WP3 Leader	UZG	Anamari Nakic
WP4 Leader	SV	Maria Sangiuliano
WP5 Leader	STU-BA	Dagmar Cagáňová

WP6 Leader	VIL	Vasiliki Madesi
WP7 Leader	VIL	Vasiliki Moutmtzi
WP8 Leader	VIL	Vasiliki Moutmtzi

Table 2: The CALIPER Project Management Team

At project coordination level:

The Project Coordinator (VIL) is responsible for the overall management and coordination of the project. ViLabs establishes a Project Coordination Team to manage the CALIPER project led by Vasiliki Moutmtzi, project coordinator and supported by Olga Katsarou, the financial manager. Apostolos Vontas, the director of ViLabs will maintain the overall view of the project. During the project lifetime other ViLabs staff members will be involved depending on their expertise. The Project Coordination Team will be specifically responsible for the following coordination tasks:

Technical coordination:

- Chairs project meetings and proposes decisions to be made based on the input from WP leaders regarding strategic orientations of the project, allocation of resources and consortium management;
- Monitors WP leadership and the achievement of project's overall objectives;
- Sets up a schedule of monthly calls with partners to track progress;
- Liaises with the EC on legal and contractual matters;
- Prepares a Consortium agreement setting out the reporting, payment and knowledge management modalities of the project;
- Signs the grant agreement on behalf of the Consortium and ensure all partners accede to the grant agreement within the timeframe specified by the EC.

Financial issues:

- Acts as the financial coordinator of the project, receiving the EC contribution to the budget and distributing this contribution according to the Grant and the Consortium Agreement;
- Provides appropriate reporting and monitoring tools to the project and follows up with the partners to ensure accurate and timely financial reporting in line with the forecast budget of the project;
- Prepares the required periodic activity and management reports for the EC summarizing progress on project tasks and deliverables and reporting any deviations and correction actions put in place.

Finally, the Project Coordinator retains the responsibility to intervene at any point of the management structure at any time when the cohesion of the project is threatened. More specifically, in case of:

- Decisions which have broader project implications and/or involve communication with the Project Officer (PO) and contradict the GA,
- Delays, costs overruns or lack of project progress against the objectives described in the GA,
- Conflicts which the WPLs are unable to resolve or whose resolution remains elusive for an extended period of time and that are threatening overall project progress.

At advisory level:

The **Advisory Board** also supports the CALIPER project during its implementation. It provides non-binding advice and support to the project activities. Its informal nature aims to ensure inclusiveness and respect for the different views which might arise regarding the evolution of the project. A representative of the Advisory Board is allowed to participate in the physical or online meetings of the Project Management Team. The Advisory Board is Coordinated by VIL. The Consortium may decide to invite further members taking into account the recommendations of EC or Advisory Board recommendations. The advisory board consists of the following members, listed in the Table 3.

#	Name	Gender	Expertise	Affiliation
1	Seppo Poutanen	Male	Academic, Sociology of science, research policy and innovations, and gender research	University of Turku, Finland
2	Britt-Marie Söderberg Torstensson	Female	EU Level women's NGO) Women's labour market participation	Winnet Sweden - Europe
3	Barbora Galvankova	Female	Programme Officer, Multilateral Organization, Gender equality and women's empowerment specialist	United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
4	Paula Wennberg	Female	Research Officer and Project Manager, Academia, Innovation and Gender platform	Luleå University of Technology, Sweden
5	David Morrow	Male	Scientific Program Manager	European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine (EATRIS)

Table 3: CALIPER Advisory Board

2.3 Communication and collaboration procedures

It is very important for the success of the project to ensure good communication among project partners and third-party entities. For the proper operation, the project should set up a fast, reliable, and easily accessible collaboration and communications infrastructure. CALIPER establishes communication through the intensive use of electronic communication tools (e.g., email, web-based project management tool, file sharing, video-conference, etc.). The project [website](#) is also used to enable fast and efficient exchanges of information.

2.3.1 Internal communication

In order to assure an efficient internal communication between partners, the CALIPER project adopts the following tools:

Physical meetings

All project partners are represented at physical consortium meetings. These meetings are chaired by the Project Coordinator. Consortium meetings are held to ensure all partners are informed of the overall progress against objectives and to ensure all partners are aware of the priorities for the next phase of development of the project. ViLabs is responsible for ensuring that consortium meetings take place at regular intervals over the duration of the project. Any concerns or suggestions put forward at Consortium meetings will be addressed in detail by the Steering Committee. The Consortium meeting is primarily a communication mechanism to ensure all partners are aware of project progress and future priorities.

The project Coordinator is responsible to organize the consortium meetings, sending an invitation and agenda to all partners and preparing and circulating the minutes to partners within 7 calendar days after the meeting. The minutes can be amended by all members participating the meeting within 3-4 days after sending the first version. The Coordinator integrates all changes and releases the final version of the minutes notifying all partners accordingly.

The time plan and location of the meeting is the following:

Type	Time	Place	Beneficiary
Project Meeting	M1-Jan 2020	Greece	VIL
Project Meeting	M6-June 2020	Croatia	UZG
Project Meeting	M12 – Dec 2020	Georgia	SRNSF
Interim Review	M18 – June 2021	Belgium	ULB
Project Meeting	M24- Dec 2021	Germany	YAE
Project Meeting	M30- June 2022	Italy	SV
Interim Review	M33- Sept 2022	Belgium	ULB
Project Meeting	M42-June 2023	Slovakia	STU BA
Final Review	M48 – Dec 2023	Belgium	ULB

Table 4: Physical meetings schedule

In order to assure an efficient internal communication between partners, the CALIPER project adopts many online tools, including the E-mail and Mailing lists, Online meeting Tool and the Project Management Tool.

E-Mail and Mailing lists

Mailing lists represent the major communication tools used in the CALIPER Project. All mailing lists are closed lists: only members registered for a particular list may send messages to the list and receive as well. To avoid unnecessary emails, each person posting to any of the email lists should ensure that the content of the message is appropriate for the recipients of the list selected. Any member may unsubscribe from any mailing list, any time.

CALIPER has already set-up and maintains the following mailing lists:

- Project mailing list with **all** partners: all@caliper-project.eu
- Project mailing list with **financial staff**: financial@caliper-project.eu

Online meeting Tool

The [GoToMeeting Tool](#) is used to organize short remote meetings between partners. Remote meetings are held every month. Additional online meetings can be arranged depending on particular needs of the project. The information related to connect to the meeting as well as the agenda is circulated not later than a couple of days before the meeting. The online meetings are also recorded, when all participants agree. The minutes are prepared in the format of the Word Document and uploaded at the Project Management Tool, within 48 hours after the online meeting.

Project Management Tool

CALIPER has set up that [Teamwork](#) to use for the project management at internal level. It is managed by the Coordinator (VIL) and offers a Collaborative Working Environment equipped by useful tools and functionalities to support collaboration within the consortium in all phases of the project. The tool allows project progress monitoring, by being constantly informed about the users' activities.

All partners involved in the project have access to the platform. The access to the platform is controlled by username and password of personal user account, which is assigned by the platform administrator (VIL). All project participants are granted access to the shared workspace. Each project partner is responsible to notify VIL of changes of project participants in their organization, in order to allow VIL to update the lists of users involved in the various work packages. Any member may also delete the account at any time.

Currently the main sections that CALIPER has set up are:

Task Boards: CALIPER organised a Board for each WP to see the flow of activities (cards) and get a fuller representation of the planned activities. Every card includes the description of the planned activity, the assigned persons, the deadline, and the progress.

Figure 2: Screenshot of Task Boards within the Project Management Tool

Milestones: CALIPER includes all project milestones, along with the Deliverables. Each record includes the description of the milestone, the involved participants, its deadline and the progress. The milestones are depicted in:

- Calendar view, which also generates a link to embed it within ones’ personal calendar
- Upcoming, shows all upcoming milestones, including milestones due today, on that project.
- Late, shows all late/overdue milestones on that project.
- Completed, shows all the completed milestones on that project.

Figure 3: Screenshot of Milestones within the Project Management Tool

The File Repository of the project: It acts as the primary means of communication for the delivery and interchange of documents, dataset and multimedia contents. To reduce the number of emails among partners, and the email size, each partner is allowed to upload files, even though VIL is in charge to give a structure to the repository. As a general principle, the documents must be uploaded to the Project

Management Tool and then announced by email; this method is preferred to sending them as attachments by email.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the File Repository within the Project Management Tool

Links: CALIPER has set up a dedicated page to concentrate the useful links that all partners need. It is very useful specially to concentrate references of rules and relevant documentation.

Figure 5: Screenshot of Links within the Project Management Tool

CHAT: CALIPER has set up a chat channel. Each member can follow the evolution of the discussions in which are interested and actively participate on tasks to carry out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the Chat within the Project Management Tool

2.3.2 External communication

The main communication channel between the CALIPER consortium and the external audience (academia and universities, industry and business, government and public sector, civil society and sister projects) will be the public CALIPER website that is developed and managed by VIL and can be accessed at <https://caliper-project.eu/>. The website contains the CALIPER overview and information about consortium. Any news relevant to the project are posted at the website automatically through the Twitter channel.

When one or a group of partners intend to submit for a scientific publication as part of work performed within the project, the partners should inform the Project Coordinator, the scientific/GEPs manager and the consortium members before the submission, by sending an email to them with the relevant information about that publication (titles, authors, abstract). Any objection from consortium partners should be made in writing Email to the Project Coordinator and the Scientific/GEPs manager within seven (7) days after receipt of the notice. Example of justified objections are: (a) the objecting Party's legitimate academic or commercial interests are compromised by the publication; (b) the protection of the objecting Party's Foreground or Background is adversely affected; (c) legal, privacy, ethical constraints are not respected. Other objections could be justified. However, any objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications. If an objection has been raised, the involved partners shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amending the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting partner shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate actions are performed following the discussion. A written acceptance shall be returned to the partner (within 2 weeks) before this partner proceeds to the submission. Moreover, the participation in exhibitions through a stand and the presentation of demos of the project results require prior agreement of the whole project Consortium. The project acknowledgment is mandatory to be included at each publication: *The present study was funded through the Project CALIPER "Linking research and innovation for gender equality" of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 873134.* In addition, each partner shall fill in the respective template "Dissemination Form" which is available from the Dissemination leader, at the common File repository.

2.4 Monitoring and reporting procedure

The project monitoring and reporting is performed by means of:

- Periodic physical and online consortium meetings
- Periodic reporting. It includes the following documents:
 - Periodic Progress Reports
 - Interim Progress Reports

Periodic progress Reports

Periodic Progress Reports will be produced within 30 days of the end of each reporting period. VIL will be in charge of preparing this and will ask each partner for any additional contributions. The project Coordinator will also submit it to the EC. It will include Technical and Administrative Issues:

- Research activities progress;
- Deliverables and milestones;
- Publications (Authors, title, publication, date);
- Conferences and presentations (Date, location, participants, subject, outcome).
- Effort on each Work package (PMs per WPs and months);
- Meetings (Date, location, subject, attendees);
- Travelling (Date, location, reason to travel, name of the traveller).

Progress reports will also contain the following information:

- a management-level overview of the activities carried out;
- a description of progress toward the scientific and technological objectives;
- a description of progress toward the milestones and deliverables foreseen;
- problems encountered during the project and actions taken to correct them.

Interim Progress Reports

Interim management reports (every 6 months, between the periodic reports) will be prepared for Consortium use. This report is intended for internal use and should help to detect early issues. The interim report will include to the following sections:

- The key results achieved by the project during the considered period (expected contribution by Work Package Leaders);
- Financial figures summarizing the main expenses: travels, equipment, etc.)
- Effort (a table presenting the used manpower).
- Project risk summary table (table to be updated continuously by each partner and WP Leader)

The time plan of the periodic reporting is the following:

Report Type	Reporting Period	Submission to Coordinator
Internal Report	M1 – M8 01/01/2020 – 31/08/2020	20 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. 20/09/2020
Official Report	M1 – M15 01/01/2020 – 31/03/2021	20 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. 20/04/2021
Internal Report	M16 – M24	20 days after the end of the reporting period,

	01/04/2021 – 31/12/2021	i.e. 20/01/2022
Official Report	M16 – M30 01/04/2021 – 30/06/2022	20 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. 20/07/2022
Internal Report	M31 – M36 01/07/2022 -31/12/2022	20 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. 20/01/2023
Internal Report	M37 – M42 01/01/2023 – 30/06/2023	20 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. 20/07/2023
Official Report	M31 – M48 01/07/2022 – 31/12/2023	20 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. 20/01/2024

Table 5: Periodic reporting time-plan

